

Management Challenges and Countermeasures of Informal Groups in Junior High Schools in the Digital Intelligence Era

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Abstract

In the digital and intelligent era, the transformation of the forms and behavioral patterns of informal groups in junior high schools poses new challenges to educational management. Existing research lacks systematic attention to their digital and intelligent characteristics and management dilemmas, and no coping strategies for the in - depth integration of technology and education have been developed. This study focuses on the informal groups in junior high school classes and employs literature review and interview methods to analyze their management dilemmas and the underlying causes. The research reveals that this group exhibits characteristics such as stable online social circles and the influence of virtual identities on behaviors, which result in the weakening of teachers' authority, the digitalization of implicit contradictions, and the ineffectiveness of traditional management. The core causes stem from the internal contradiction between technological empowerment and control and the generational gap in digital literacy, manifested as the disconnection between educational needs and management, the failure of the role - model mechanism, and the insufficient collaboration among schools, families, and communities. Based on this, the research proposes constructing a digital and intelligent monitoring and early-warning mechanism, implementing online-offline collaborative guidance, designing a program to enhance teachers' digital capabilities, building a participatory management model, and establishing a collaborative governance framework involving schools, families, and communities. The research indicates that managing it requires coordinating technological and humanistic values. By enhancing teachers' digital literacy, optimizing hierarchical strategies, and strengthening collaboration to overcome difficulties, it offers practical approaches and theoretical references for the digital and intelligent transformation of class management.

Keywords: Digital Era; Junior high school students; informal groups

1. Introduction

The advent of the digital and intelligent era has spurred the accelerated transformation of the education sector. The "Outline of the Plan for Building a Strong Education Country (2024 - 2035)" has elevated education digitization to a national strategy, emphasizing the reconstruction of the education governance system using technologies such as artificial intelligence and blockchain. However, at the policy level, key issues like the boundaries of education data collection and the ethical norms for home - school collaboration remain undefined. There is inadequate support for teachers' digital literacy, and there's a lack of systematic response plans for new phenomena such as online social circles.

In practice, the informal groups formed by junior high school students via social software and game platforms exhibit complex characteristics. On one hand, they help expand social networks and stimulate creativity; on the other hand, there are issues such as internet addiction and the spread of harmful information. Schools and teachers are confronted with management dilemmas, including ineffective guidance and a breakdown in home - school collaboration. This research aims to uncover the core characteristics and interaction logic of informal groups in junior high schools during the digital and intelligent era through interviews. It focuses on the management dilemmas they face and analyzes the underlying causes. Finally, it proposes practical coping strategies to lay the foundation for constructing a management system tailored to the digital and intelligent era.

At the theoretical level, this research can broaden the micro - perspective of educational management theory. By elucidating the impact of digital and intelligent technologies on group behavior, it enriches the theory in the "technology - education" cross - field. Based on humanism and Bandura's social learning theory, it reveals the profound changes in the power structure between teachers and students and the psychological needs of groups, thus improving the theoretical system of informal group management. Meanwhile, it promotes the integration of educational management theory with technological theories such as artificial intelligence and big data, offering a reference for the digital transformation of educational governance. At the practical level, the research will offer frontline teachers an actionable identification checklist and intervention strategies to enable them to precisely pinpoint problems. It will help schools set up a scientific digital management system, facilitating the transformation of the management model from experience-based judgment to data-driven decision-making. Moreover, by analyzing the micro-level implementation paths of the Outline for the Construction of a Strong Education Country, it will put forward a student-centered participatory management model and a home-school-community collaboration framework to support the implementation of the national education digitalization strategy and promote the establishment of a healthy social ecosystem for adolescents.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Current situation of foreign research

Foreign scholars' research on junior high school informal groups focuses on the technology - driven transformation of behavior patterns, innovation in management strategies, and cross - cultural adaptability challenges. Rodríguez & Chaux (2021) found through qualitative research that the conflict dynamics of adolescent online informal groups are characterized by anonymity, rapid spread, and delayed third - party intervention. Conflicts often quickly escalate from verbal friction to cyber violence, and the social identity needs of group members exacerbate the intensification of contradictions (Rodríguez & Chaux, 2021). The meta - analysis by Gaffney et al. (2021) further pointed out that effective anti - bullying programs need to integrate intelligent tools such as natural language processing (NLP) with peer intervention mechanisms (Gaffney et al., 2021). However, current research still lacks a systematic solution for monitoring implicit conflicts (such as cold violence and group exclusion) in virtual communities.

Technological empowerment has a dual effect on the behavioral reconstruction of informal groups. Based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), (Nawaz et al., 2017) proposed that students' participation in social learning groups is highly correlated with their perceived "usefulness" and "ease of use". However, the openness of technology may lead to the alienation of group goals. For example, the "learning mutual - assistance groups" spontaneously formed by students may evolve into a trading platform for cheating tools due to the lack of supervision. Costello & Hope (2016) used a mixed - research method and found that peer influence has a two - way nature in an anonymous environment. On the one hand, students are more likely to be affected by negative behaviors (such as cyberbullying). On the other hand, the involvement of virtual tutors can significantly enhance the soundness of group norms through positive guidance. For instance, pushing cooperation cases via AI can reinforce prosocial behaviors.

Cultural differences and contradictions in technology ethics are the core challenges in current research. Tolstykh's (2014) research on Russian adolescent groups indicates that virtual identities reinforce implicit obedience in a collectivist culture. Students are more likely to resolve conflicts through group consensus rather than publicly voicing individual opinions, which stands in sharp contrast to the "freedom of individual expression" emphasized in Western research. In addition, the risk of "labeling intervention" proposed by Lynam (1978) earlier has been further magnified in the digital and intelligent era. Algorithm - driven group classification may exacerbate the trust crisis between teachers and students. For example, if an intelligent monitoring tool misidentifies a normal interest group as a high - risk group, it may lead to excessive intervention by teachers and the neglect of students' real needs.

In terms of management strategies, foreign scholars have proposed a "technology - humanity" collaborative governance framework. Gaffney et al. (2021) suggested developing an NLP - based early - warning system to identify high - risk conversations (such as insults and self - harm tendencies) in real time, and combine it with teachers' manual assessment for graded responses. For example, keywords related to insults can trigger psychological counseling intervention. Rodríguez & Chaux (2021) emphasize the guiding mechanism of integrating the virtual and the real. For example, they propose to translate the collaborative ability within game groups into offline practical activities (such as campus environmental protection projects) to enhance the real - world transfer of positive behaviors. In response to cultural differences, Costello & Hope (2016) put forward an indirect intervention strategy. For instance, they suggest having virtual tutors anonymously mediate conflicts to avoid group exclusion in the context of the "face culture" in East Asia.

However, there are still obvious limitations in the existing research. On the one hand, over - reliance on technological tools may lead to "management alienation" and overlook the emotional support function of informal groups (Tolstykh, 2014). On the other hand, the adaptability of Western intervention strategies (such as openly discussing conflicts) in non - Western cultures urgently needs to be verified. Future research should enhance interdisciplinary integration, find the balance between algorithm transparency and privacy protection, and build a full - cycle management ecosystem of "need identification - behavior guidance - resource support" in line with local practices.

2.2 Current situation of domestic research

As of March 1, 2025, a search was carried out in the CNKI academic journal database with the keyword "informal groups", yielding a total of 2,318 documents. A visual analysis of the search results reveals that research on informal groups in China started in the 1980s. After 2000, an increasing number of scholars have focused on the study of informal groups. In recent years, the research perspectives of relevant documents have become more diverse, the research contents have grown richer, and the research methods have gradually diversified. Meanwhile, there are still some limitations.

The formation of informal groups in junior high schools is influenced by multiple factors. Fang (2024) found through questionnaire surveys and interviews that it mainly results from students' similar physical and mental development stages and personality traits. These groups are characterized by spontaneity, coordination, and instability. Wan (2020) pointed out that the formation of high - school students' informal groups is mainly based on factors such as similar interests, personality attraction, and close spatial proximity. Wang (2022) argues that the formation of informal groups in junior high school classes is closely associated with factors such as students' participation in class activities, teacher - student communication, and home - school cooperation. These studies suggest that the formation of informal groups in junior high schools is a complex psychological and social process, comprehensively affected by multiple factors. Informal groups in junior high schools have distinctive characteristics, which are more pronounced in the digital and intelligent era. Guo (2024) pointed out that informal groups wield significant influence within the class. Their behavior patterns and ways of interaction have a profound impact on the class atmosphere and the individual development of students. Through case analysis, Wang (2024) discovered that junior high school students' informal groups exhibit

different behavioral traits in terms of gender. Boys' groups tend to favor rigid management, whereas girls' groups require more flexible management. Additionally, Liu (2022) noted that in the Internet age, junior high school students' informal groups have given rise to new "circles" such as "fan circles" and "game circles". These groups are characterized by being closed - off, exclusive, and inducing consumption. These studies indicate that junior high school informal groups exhibit new characteristics in the digital and intelligent age, such as being network - based, interest - driven, and having gender differences.

Junior high school informal groups have a two - fold impact on students' growth and class management. On the one hand, informal groups can satisfy students' psychological needs, facilitate socialization, and enliven class life; on the other hand, they may also cause psychological or behavioral deviations among students and undermine the cohesion of the class. Mao (2024) discovered through action research that students in negative informal groups can make remarkable progress in behavioral norms, learning engagement, and social interaction through effective intervention measures. Zhang (2024) pointed out that negative informal groups are widespread in county - level secondary vocational schools, and managing them requires the collaborative efforts of families, schools, and society. These studies indicate that the influence of informal groups in junior high schools is two - sided, and educators need to offer scientific guidance and management.

Informal groups in junior high schools can be categorized into positive, intermediate, and negative types based on their nature and behavioral characteristics. Wang and Huang (2014) pointed out that informal groups in regular high schools can be divided into these three categories, and the influence of intermediate groups on class management is relatively complex. Dong (2012) discovered through empirical research that the formation and evolution of high - school students' informal groups are affected by various factors, and their characteristics also differ according to the group type. Additionally, Zhu (1997) conducted an exploration of the "anti - class informal groups" and pointed out that such groups present significant challenges to class management. These studies indicate that junior high school informal groups come in a variety of types, and educators need to carry out classified management and provide guidance based on specific circumstances.

In response to the management challenges of informal groups in junior high schools, scholars have proposed various countermeasures. Fang (2024) suggests that homeroom teachers should recognize and effectively guide informal groups, improve the school management system, and establish an educational community involving schools, families, and the community. Wang (2022) proposes that teachers should focus on self - development, actively engage in class activities, break down the communication barriers between teachers and students, leverage the role of core members, and establish a home - school cooperation education mechanism. Liu (2022) emphasizes that educational administrators can implement management through strategies such as standardizing students' perception of "cliques", conducting consumption education, and meeting students' daily social needs. In addition, through narrative research, Huang Hongsheng (2020) found that transforming negative informal groups with a sense of class mission is an effective strategy. These studies suggest that managing informal groups in junior high schools calls for the comprehensive use of multiple strategies and intervention and guidance from multiple levels, including schools, families, and society.

In conclusion, the formation, characteristics, influence, types, and management strategies of junior high school informal groups present a complex and systematic issue. In the context of the digital - intelligence era, educators should adopt scientific and reasonable management approaches to promote the all - around development of junior high school students and optimize class management. Future research can further examine the new features and trends of junior high school informal groups in the digital - intelligence era, explore more accurate and effective management methods, and offer more targeted theoretical support and practical guidance for junior high school education management.

3. Method

3.1 Research Methods

Literature Review Method This study employs the literature review method to systematically organize the theoretical foundation and research approaches regarding the management challenges and countermeasures for junior high school informal groups in the digital intelligence era. When it comes to Chinese literature, databases like CNKI are utilized to conduct both precise and fuzzy searches using keywords such as "Digital Intelligence Era", "Junior High School Informal Groups", and "Educational Management", with a focus on research findings in the fields of educational management and educational technology. For foreign literature, keywords such as "Digital Intelligence Era" and "Junior High School Informal Groups" are used to search for international studies in databases like Web of Science. The Chinese and foreign literature is then sorted, categorized, and analyzed to uncover theoretical support and broaden the research perspective and depth.

Interview Method A semi-structured interview approach was employed. Through direct dialogues between teachers and students, the current state of managing informal groups in junior high schools in the digital and intelligent age was analyzed, and the root causes of challenges and corresponding coping strategies were explored. Teacher interviews concentrated on the manifestations of the weakening of teacher authority, situations where traditional management proved ineffective, and barriers to the application of digital and intelligent technologies. Student interviews focused on preferences for online social platforms, group communication topics, and the influence of online behaviors on values. Through multi - angle information collection, a theoretical and practical foundation was provided for the establishment of a management system.

Research ethics: Prior to the interview, the questions were explained to the research participants, and written records were taken after their consent was obtained. After the interview, it was promised that the information would solely be used for research purposes, and privacy information (such as names of individuals and schools) would be anonymized.

3.2 Research Design

The interviews aim to gain an in - depth understanding of the actual situation of junior high school informal group management in the digital and intelligent era and obtain rich and authentic first - hand information to support the research. Teachers and students from two junior high schools were selected as interviewees. The teachers include homeroom teachers and subject teachers. They are in close contact with informal groups in daily teaching and class management and can provide information on management dilemmas and obstacles in technology application. The students include core members and ordinary members of informal groups. As direct participants within the groups, they have a profound understanding of the group interaction patterns and the impact of online socializing.

The interviews were conducted in a targeted manner. For students, semi - structured interviews in a relaxed chatting style were adopted. They were not informed in advance to create a natural communication atmosphere. The key questions included the reasons for group formation, the use of online platforms (commonly used platforms, communication frequency and content), the impact of online socializing on behavior and values, and their feelings and expectations regarding teachers' management methods. The investigation was carried out gradually from the individual to the group to the class, and deeper information was probed. For homeroom teachers and subject teachers, one - on - one semi - structured interviews were used. The purpose was explained in advance, and their cooperation was requested. The interviews revolved around management challenges in the digital and intelligent era, the use of technological tools (types of tools, technological difficulties), and their understanding of student groups. Follow - up questions were asked based on the answers to obtain rich information.

4. Results

4.1 Results of the interview implementation

In this study, interviews were conducted with four junior high school teachers (two homeroom teachers and two subject teachers) and four junior high school students (two core members of informal groups and two ordinary members) to gain a detailed understanding of the current situation, problems, and expectations regarding the management of junior high school informal groups in the digital - intelligence era. The basic information of the interviewed teachers and students is as follows:

Table. 1 Basic information of the interviewed teachers and students

Interview subject type	Interview subject	Grade	School	Subject (teacher) / Whether a core member (student)
Homeroom teacher	Teacher T1	Grade 8	S Middle School	Politics and Law
Homeroom teacher	Teacher T2	Grade 8	F Middle School	Mathematics
Subject teacher	Teacher K1	Grade 7	S Middle School	Politics and Law
Subject teacher	Teacher K2	Grade 8	F Middle School	Chinese
Student	Core member S1	Grade 8	S Middle School	Yes
Student	Core member S2	Grade 7	F Middle School	Yes
Student	Regular member S3	Grade 8	S Middle School	No
Student	Regular member S4	Grade 7	F Middle School	No

4.1.1 Management dilemmas from the teachers' perspective

From the teachers' perspective, managing junior high school informal groups in the digital - intelligence era faces numerous challenges.

First, it's difficult to monitor online behavior. Teacher T1 pointed out that online social circles have made the relationships among students more complex, thus increasing the management difficulty. For example, some students in the class have formed an "anime lovers" group on Douyin and Bilibili, sharing a great deal of anime - related content on these platforms, some of which is negative. However, due to teachers' limited energy, it's impossible to conduct comprehensive monitoring, making it hard to ensure that students aren't affected by the negative content. Teacher T2 mentioned that virtual identities make it difficult to regulate students' behavior within the group. Some students have posted inappropriate remarks on anonymous social platforms, disrupting the class order. However, it's difficult to trace their real identities, making it hard to implement educational punishments.

Second, there's inadequate adaptation of technological tools. Teacher K1 said that the effectiveness of traditional management measures has significantly declined in the digital and intelligent era. In the past, methods like formulating class rules and regulations and holding class - meeting education had little impact on regulating online group behavior. Students in the online environment often aren't restricted by these rules and still act as they wish. Teacher K2 reported

that there are technical hurdles when using digital and intelligent technologies to manage student groups. They have limited knowledge of some emerging social software and management tools, don't know how to leverage these tools to analyze student group behavior, and it's also difficult to detect potential problems promptly through technical means. Teacher T1 frankly admitted, "I'm not familiar with emerging platforms like Kuaishou and Lofter. Once, I mistook the normal communication in the student movie activity editing group for idle chat. I only realized it was a misunderstanding after I criticized them." Traditional management methods such as class meetings for lecturing and disciplinary punishments are almost ineffective for online group behavior. Teacher T2 once formulated an online convention requiring civilized language, but students used "alt accounts" or anonymous channels to avoid supervision. "If you ban one group, they'll immediately rebuild it on another platform. It's simply out of control."

Third, there is a breakdown in home - school collaboration, and the boundary of responsibilities is blurred. Teacher T1 found that few parents actively inquire about their children's online group dynamics. "Most parents only care about their children's academic performance. They don't know what their children are chatting about on QQ groups or Douyin. Some even think that 'as long as it doesn't affect their studies, it's fine'. It's only when their children become addicted or are affected by inappropriate information that they finally wake up to the reality." K2 teachers suggest establishing a school-family data sharing platform, but they're confronted with the issue of privacy protection: "Parents are concerned about excessive monitoring of their children, and schools lack compliant technical means. Currently, communication can only be conducted sporadically through irregular parent-teacher meetings, failing to form a synergy."

4.1.2 Group situation from the students' perspective

Students form informal groups primarily because of shared interests and emotional bonds. Online social platforms have made it convenient for them to form such groups. They frequently use QQ, WeChat, Douyin, and Kuaishou to communicate, spending an average of 1 - 2 hours a day. The content of their communication encompasses sharing interests, discussing homework, and having daily interactions. S1 said that their "anime lovers" group communicates via Douyin. Apart from sharing anime news, they also discuss anime characters and plotlines together, which has allowed them to make many like-minded friends. Meanwhile, they chat about anime plotlines and share fan art in the QQ group, and they even won a prize in the school painting competition together. S3 mentioned that although online socializing is convenient, there are also some problems. For example, there are occasional quarrels in the group, and some members may post radical remarks online, which affects the group atmosphere. S2 believes that online socializing has had a significant impact on group behavior. On the Internet, people are more willing to express their opinions, and sometimes intense debates may break out due to different views. Moreover, online socializing enriches group activities, such as forming teams for online games and checking in for online learning. S4 said that they noticed some classmates procrastinated on their homework because they were addicted to chatting in the game group: "They stayed up late at night discussing tactics and were sleepy in class the next day, and the teacher didn't even know why." At the same time, S4 also hopes that teachers can understand their activities in informal groups, not always ban them, but provide correct guidance.

4.1.3 Teachers' and students' expectations for management

Teachers expect the school to offer more training on the application of digital and intelligent technologies to improve their ability to manage online groups. T3 teachers hope the school will introduce specialized software for monitoring students' online behavior to help them detect students' bad behavior tendencies in a timely manner. K3 teachers expect to strengthen collaborative management with parents to jointly guide students to use the Internet properly and prevent them from getting addicted to the Internet or being affected by harmful information.

On the other hand, students hope teachers will adopt a more flexible and empathetic management style. They hope teachers will reduce direct intervention and be more involved in guiding them. S1 suggested, "Teachers can join our discussions about game characters and share positive stories about the characters' backgrounds. This is more effective than directly banning us from playing games." S2 hopes that teachers will respect the interests and hobbies of their informal groups and not easily dismiss them. The ordinary member S3 said frankly, "We encourage each other and share our stress in the group. This kind of peer support is very important to us. Teachers can keep an eye on us, but don't always try to break us up. Give us some space to manage ourselves."

4.2 Core characteristics of informal groups in junior high schools

Against the backdrop of the digital and intelligent era, informal groups in junior high schools feature prominently in the stratification of online social circles, the alienation of behavior under virtual identities, strong interest orientation, and high dynamic mobility. The specific manifestations are as follows:

4.2.1 Stability of online social circles

Students form closed interest circles on platforms such as QQ, Douyin, and Lofter, with frequent interaction within the group and an exclusive nature. For example, the members of an "anime group" in a certain class prefer to communicate on Douyin, sharing fan creations, plot discussions, etc., thus forming a cultural symbol system independent of the formal class group. Inside the circle, a sense of belonging is strengthened through exclusive jargon and virtual identities, while an information barrier is created against the outside world (such as teachers and non-member students), making it difficult for teachers to get involved in real interaction scenarios.

4.2.2 There are many virtual identities.

In anonymous social scenarios (such as the anonymous function in QQ groups and virtual account systems), the direct impact of real-world identities is diminished. Some students tend to showcase personalized ways of expression that are rarely seen in offline social interactions. For example, members of a particular game community often interact via virtual characters, and some users transfer the interaction patterns from the online context to real-world social scenarios. Meanwhile, the creation of virtual avatars on short-video platforms has also become a means for teenagers to express their personalized viewpoints. The multiplicity of digital identities presents technical challenges for educators when tracking and identifying group behavior patterns. Traditional approaches to behavior management and discipline need to be adjusted to fit the new online interaction environment.

4.2.3 Coexistence of Interest Aggregation and Dynamic Adaptation

The establishment of online communities is primarily based on the bond of shared interests (such as photography technique exchanges, programming studies, and discussions on anime and manga culture). The activity cycles of these communities naturally fluctuate, and their forms may be adjusted as members' focus shifts or the participation of key members changes. For instance, in a campus image-creation community, as some highly active members entered a new academic phase, the focus of group interaction gradually shifted towards discussions on diverse topics. The development of digital technology has created opportunities for group diversity. Students can concurrently engage in various spaces, including academic exchange communities, entertainment social groups, and interest-based communities, according to their different needs, thus forming a multi-dimensional social participation model.

5. Discussion

5.1 Analysis of the management dilemmas of informal junior high school groups

5.1.1 Online behavior management: The supervision dilemma posed by virtual identities

The anonymity of virtual identities and the nature of cross - platform socializing present multiple challenges to the supervision of the online behaviors of informal junior high school groups. In an anonymous setting, students' behaviors undergo significant changes: Some students exhibit aggression that is rarely seen in real life in situations like anonymous QQ groups and "alt accounts" in games. For instance, members of an anonymous class group frequently post abusive comments, and it's difficult to impose disciplinary penalties as the real identities cannot be traced. Moreover, some students discuss the plots of violent games in anonymous game groups and imitate the characters' language, which disrupts classroom order. Due to the lack of an immediate punishment mechanism for such behaviors, a cognitive bias of "no consequences for actions" has gradually taken shape, exacerbating the disorder in group interactions.

The adaptability of traditional regulatory measures is significantly lacking in the digital and intelligent era. Norms such as online civilized language conventions established by teachers are often evaded by students through the "cross - platform migration" strategy. For example, after teachers banned group creation on WeChat, students quickly re - formed groups on platforms like Lofter. Screening inappropriate information in Douyin's anime groups requires a huge amount of effort but can hardly cover high - frequency interactive content. This "restriction - transfer" cycle reveals the inherent limitations of offline rules in regulating online behaviors, and the authority of traditional management measures has been greatly undermined in the virtual space. The backwardness of technological tools further restricts the effectiveness of supervision. The interviewed teachers generally reported a lack of intelligent monitoring tools and could only conduct management through extensive methods such as keyword blocking. For example, a teacher, unfamiliar with the functions of the Lofter platform, mistakenly judged the students' normal video - editing exchanges as "idle chatting" and criticized them, highlighting the real - world contradiction that teachers' technical capabilities lag behind students' social innovation. The shortage of technological tools and operational blind spots not only lead to frequent management misjudgments but also make it difficult for teachers to accurately identify and intervene in group behavior, resulting in a passive situation where they "want to manage but can't reach all, and manage inaccurately".

5.1.2 Emotional connection management: The conflict between students' needs and educational goals

In the digital and intelligent era, there is an obvious conflict between educators' understanding of the functions of informal groups and students' actual needs, mainly manifested in three aspects: First, the emotional support function is ignored. Schools and families often judge the value of groups solely from the perspective of "whether it affects academic performance", overlooking the role of informal groups as a channel for students to vent their stress. For example, some students encourage each other and relieve anxiety through voice chats in study mutual - assistance groups, yet teachers consider such interactions a waste of time. This cognitive bias fails to meet students' emotional needs in formal settings like classrooms. Instead, students become more reliant on online groups, weakening the emotional bond between teachers and students.

Secondly, students' self - management ability is suppressed. Teachers are often wary of informal groups and tend to completely dismiss students' self - management behaviors. For instance, Teacher T2 once insisted on dissolving an anime group spontaneously organized by students. As a result, students resorted to underground socializing, and the group cohesion developed in a negative way. Students' enthusiasm for independently formulating group rules and

organizing activities has been dampened, and the development of their initiative and self - management abilities has also been hindered as a result.

Finally, there is a contradiction between interest value and educational evaluation. Creative activities of informal groups such as anime groups and game groups, like fan creation and offline cosplay, are often prohibited because they have nothing to do with learning, which causes dissatisfaction among students. For example, the actions of the group that S1 belongs to, such as creating anime fan - art and organizing activities, were not recognized but rather restricted. This reflects teachers' lack of understanding of emerging sub - cultures, leading to a disconnect between management methods and students' needs and intensifying the conflict between the two sides.

5.1.3 Home - school collaborative management: The contradiction between the boundary of responsibility and technology application

Home - school collaborative management faces dual challenges of responsibility division and technology application in the digital and intelligent era. First, there is the issue of delayed supervision caused by information asymmetry. Most parents are unfamiliar with the social platforms commonly used by students, and only a small number of families actively monitor the dynamics of online groups. For example, S4's academic performance declined because they stayed up late chatting in a gaming group. The parents didn't notice the problem until the parent - teacher meeting. By then, the behavior had become habitual and was hard to correct. The untimely information exchange between schools and families often causes risk intervention to miss the optimal time, indicating the lack of daily supervision.

Secondly, the structural deficiency in parents' digital literacy restricts management efficiency. Most parents' usage of online protection tools, such as the "youth mode", remains at a basic level, and they are unable to recognize hidden risks like the value infiltration in gaming groups. Some parents resort to simple and crude measures like "confiscating devices", which, however, trigger parent - child conflicts. As a result, students are prompted to turn to places such as Internet cafes to continue their group activities, further complicating the management. The disparities between schools and families in terms of technological awareness and intervention methods highlight the complexity of collaborative governance in the digital and intelligent age.

5.2 Analysis of the causes of the management dilemma of junior high school informal groups

The emergence of the management dilemma of junior high school informal groups in the digital and intelligent age is the result of the interplay of multiple factors, including the application of educational theories, the characteristics of technological development, and the coordination of social systems. Specifically, it can be analyzed from two aspects: theoretical roots and era - related conflicts:

5.2.1 Theoretical roots: The profound disconnection between educational theories and group behaviors

Bandura's social learning theory indicates that the anonymity of virtual identities weakens the "immediate link between behavior and consequences". For example, it's hard to trace and punish students who post abusive remarks in anonymous groups. This cognitive bias that negative behaviors carry no costs can trigger group imitation and lead to the spread of negative behaviors. The humanistic theory reveals that when teachers ignore the emotional support function of informal groups, students' "need for respect" can't be met in reality, so they turn to seeking compensation through virtual identities. In addition, both Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory and Bandura's self - efficacy theory point out that when teachers completely deny students' self - management behaviors, it will suppress students' sense of belonging and self - identity, make them have a negative assessment of their own abilities, and hinder individual development.

5.2.2 Inducements of the era: The structural conflict between digital and intelligent technologies and the educational ecosystem

There is a significant contradiction between the openness of digital and intelligent technologies and the closed - off nature of educational management. The algorithm recommendation mechanisms of platforms like Douyin and Kuaishou may reinforce homogeneous content. However, schools are restricted by data privacy policies and lack the proper authorization to obtain students' online behavior data, making it difficult for traditional supervision methods to intervene precisely.

Meanwhile, there is a "cultural decoding gap" between teachers and students. Teachers have little understanding of emerging sub - cultures such as the "fan circle" and the "gaming circle." They tend to view the fan creations in anime groups as having nothing to do with learning and ignore their creative expression value, which leads to a misalignment between management strategies and students' real needs.

At the policy level, although the Outline of the Plan for Building a Strong Education Country mentions digital governance, it does not clarify the ethical boundaries of data sharing between schools and families, such as the scope of parents' right to know. The traditional model of "schools leading and families supporting" struggles to meet the professional requirements of online group management, and school - family collaboration has fallen into a management dilemma due to the lack of an operating guide. This section identifies the core challenges faced by informal junior high school groups in the digital age from three perspectives: online behavior management, emotional connection management, and home-school collaboration. It then analyzes the causes from two aspects: theoretical underpinnings and contemporary factors. The research indicates that to overcome these challenges, a three-dimensional governance framework of "technical monitoring - humanistic guidance - home-school collaboration" should be established based on respect for the emotional needs and growth patterns of these groups. This framework will lay a theoretical foundation for the subsequent formulation of coping strategies.

5.3 Coping Strategies for Informal Groups in Junior High Schools in the Digital and Intelligent Era

In response to the management dilemmas revealed by the interviews and guided by humanistic theory and Bandura's social learning theory, this study proposes coping strategies from three dimensions: technological empowerment, humanistic guidance, and home - school collaboration, aiming to construct a three - dimensional management system of "identification - guidance - transformation".

5.3.1 Technological Empowerment: Digital and Intelligent Monitoring and Guidance

To address the issues of difficult online supervision and inadequate adaptation of technological tools reported by teachers, technological empowerment is needed to improve the accuracy of management. Schools can introduce an intelligent management system to integrate the behavioral data from students' commonly used social platforms, including usage duration, keyword frequency, and interaction patterns. Algorithms can automatically identify potential risks, such as the spread of harmful information and excessive addiction, and issue real - time warnings to teachers. For example, when the system detects frequent use of violent words in a gaming group or late - night activity in the group, it automatically alerts the class teacher to intervene and provide guidance, thus avoiding the limitations and delays associated with manual supervision. Meanwhile, to address the technical operation challenges faced by teachers, specialized training courses are offered. The courses cover understanding the functions of mainstream social platforms, risk - identification techniques, and the use of basic data tools. Through case simulations, teachers' practical skills in using technical tools are enhanced, and management misjudgments due to technical blind spots are minimized, enabling technology to truly serve as an aid for management rather than a hindrance.

5.3.2 *Emotional guidance: Return to the student as the main body*

Based on the humanistic theory's emphasis on students' emotional needs and subjective initiative, teachers should shift from being authoritative supervisors to becoming listeners for students. Actively integrate into students' informal groups, such as joining class game groups and anime discussion groups. Initiate positive topics as a like-minded partner. For example, in the game group, guide discussions on how teamwork strategies can be applied in real life, or in the anime group, share the themes of growth in classic works. Naturally integrate interest-related content with value guidance to avoid the resistance that simple prohibitions may trigger.

Utilize Bandura's social learning theory to tap into the positive factors within the group. Identify the positive behaviors of core members (such as the offline learning mutual-assistance activities organized by the group where S1 is located). Reinforce the role-model effect through class announcements and awarding the "Group Positive Energy Award" to stimulate the motivation of other members to imitate. Meanwhile, introduce external cases, such as inviting outstanding graduates to share how to balance interests and studies. This can help students establish positive behavior patterns in group interactions, transform the collaborative and creative abilities developed in virtual social interactions into real-world growth resources, and turn informal groups into a practical arena for cultivating social skills and self-management.

5.3.3 *Collaborative education: Clarify the division of labor between schools and families*

To address the issue of the disconnection in school-family collaboration, establish a three-party cooperation mechanism of "school technical monitoring - parents' daily attention - students' self-management". Schools should regularly provide feedback to parents via a secure data-sharing platform on students' participation in informal groups, including the main topics of communication and time allocation. Parents, on their part, should use the platform to share the behavioral changes they observe at home, such as mood swings and interest shifts, to avoid one-sided supervision that focuses solely on academic scores. Establish parent digital literacy classes to guide parents on the reasonable use of screen time management tools, help them understand the dual impacts of online social interaction on teenagers, and avoid over-controlling or being laissez-faire. For example, regarding the issue of "being addicted to chatting in game groups" mentioned in S4, schools can provide a template of the "game time schedule", and parents should cooperate in supervision. Meanwhile, teachers should guide classroom discussions on "how to cultivate self-discipline in one's interests" to form a consistent guiding direction between schools and families.

By signing the "Home-School Collaboration Convention", clearly define the boundaries of privacy protection and the scope of information sharing, balance supervision and respect, and enable parents to shift from passive cooperation to active participation, so as to jointly create a healthy online social environment for students. In short, technology empowers the resolution of basic regulatory problems, humanistic guidance addresses core emotional needs, and home-school collaboration resolves key mechanism issues. These three aspects complement each other and form an educational synergy. Ultimately, precise guidance can be achieved, turning informal groups in the digital and intelligent era into positive carriers for promoting students' social growth rather than management burdens.

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